

UGC Approved Journal No – 40957

(IIJIF) Impact Factor- 4.172

Regd. No. : 1687-2006-2007

ISSN 0974 - 7648

J I G Y A S A

**AN INTERDISCIPLINARY REFEREED
RESEARCH JOURNAL**

Chief Editor : *Indukant Dixit*

Executive Editor : *Shashi Bhushan Poddar*

Editor
Reeta Yadav

Volume 12

February 2019

No. 2

Published by
PODDAR FOUNDATION
Taranagar Colony
Chhittupur, BHU, Varanasi
www.jigyasabhu.blogspot.com
www.jigyasabhu.com
E-mail : jigyasabhu@gmail.com
Mob. 9415390515, 0542 2366370

Contents

- **Maya in “Cry, The Peacock”** **1-5**
Dr. Vinod Kumar Mishra, Associate Professor,
I.G.P.G. College, Gauriganj, Amethi
- **Mental Health: A Descriptive Analysis** **6-9**
Udayan Misra, Associate Professor, Deptt. of
Psychology, Harishchandra P.G. College, Varanasi
- **Academic Anxiety as a Function of Some
Demographic Factors** **10-19**
Dr. Medha, Assistant Professor, Amity University
Utter Pradesh, Noida
- **Bridging the Gap between Home Language and
School Language from English Teachers’
Perspective** **20-25**
Kanchan Singh, Research Scholar, Faculty of
Education (K), BHU, Varanasi
- **Effect of Sex, Locale and Education on
Adjustment, Selfesteem and Depression** **26-33**
Sudha Singh, Research Scholar, Psychology, S. R. K.
P. G. College, Firozabad
- **War on Terror in Afghanistan and the Prospect
of Peace** **34-39**
Swati Kumari, Research Scholar, Center for Russian
and Central Asian Studies, School for International
Studies, JNU, New Delhi
- **Climate Induced Migration and Food Security
Crisis in Bangladesh** **40-45**
Sachin Kumar Singh, Research Scholar, Malviya
Centre for Peace Research BHU, Varanasi
- **Street Food: A Discourse on the Food Safety
and Standards Act, 2006 to Ensure Safety of
Street Food and Protection of Health of its
Consumers in India** **46-53**
Kamal Kishore Chandak, Ph.D. Scholar, Department
of Law, Gauhati University, Guwahati, Assam

War on Terror in Afghanistan and the Prospect of Peace

Swati Kumari *

The attacks of 9/11 brought the post-Cold War era to an end ushering in an era where the world had a common enemy – Terrorism particularly Islamic Terrorism. In response to one of the most horrific attacks on American soil, the United States attacked Afghanistan and ousted the Taliban-led government from Kabul for sheltering the mastermind of 9/11 – al-Qaeda's Osama bin Laden. On 20th September 2001, the Bush administration announced War on Terror in Afghanistan which would not stop until all the terrorists of the world are found and defeated¹. US-led NATO forces invaded Afghanistan invoking Article 5 of the treaty². Air-strikes on al-Qaeda and Taliban training camps were launched from October 7, and by the end of the month almost all major countries of West and Europe³ had deployed their troops in Afghanistan, starting the ground war that continues till date. Out of all the wars the Americans have fought on foreign soil, this one – in Afghanistan seems to be never ending. The war has witnessed a change of three Presidential terms in US but other than killing Osama bin Laden after ten years since the beginning of the attacks, calling US's military campaign a success is highly debatable.

Today the United States is involved in peace talks with the same enemy – the Taliban it once swore to decimate. This article tries to evaluate the US-led war on Terror in Afghanistan on its successes and failures with regard to the objectives it began in the first place. It examines how the real situation, the real fight between the International forces and Taliban militants more than bringing any actual change has led to unfathomable misery and deaths to the local population. Terrorism is not something that is new to the world; its origin can be traced back to the 66 AD, to the *sicarii*⁴ or dagger-wielders of Palestine (Rappaport, 1982). The face of terrorists might have changed, the methods of attack might have changed, but what still remains the same is the violence and fear that they draw in. Before going into further discussion let us first understand what terrorism is. Till date a comprehensive and legal definition of

* Research Scholar, Center for Russian and Central Asian Studies, School for International Studies, JNU, New Delhi

terrorism has not been agreed upon by the international community. The reason being, the pejorative that surrounds the world leaders when it comes to terrorism. Each country defines and understands terrorism in a different way, then comes the problem of differentiating between insurgency and terrorism, if that is somehow overcome other challenge is posed by the various discourses of terrorism. The major trouble came up when US supported and financed the Mujahedeen against the Soviet army, later when this group splintered and formed Taliban with which US is still fighting, highlighted a very contradictory position of the United States regarding the same terrorist organization. When the attacks of 9/11 jolted the world and America led the War on Terror, where terror was defined unilaterally⁵; no questions were raised against any of the actions taken by Washington, because the widespread emotions that were aroused post 9/11 gave a firm ground and opportunity to construct a framework and outline of what terrorism was according to the West.

Before 9/11 the world community had no clear approach to deal with Afghanistan or particularly Taliban. There have been a few indirect military confrontations by Washington and Iran and also an imposition of arms embargo, which could not be pursued owing to porous borders between Pakistan and Afghanistan⁶. The international community had chosen to ignore or rather not see in the direction as Taliban went on violating all the international laws, human rights and so on. The list of inhumanity and atrocities included treating women as second-class citizens, extrusion of all international agencies and NGO's, mass abuse and persecution of religious and ethnic minorities, gross human rights violations, cultural vandalism which was in the form of destructing the Bamian Buddhas and other artifacts of the country's non-Islamic heritage, promotion of an illicit economy with networks covering the whole of Central Asia and Russia including opium trade and production, and finally providing a safe haven for militants to train and launch offensives from Afghanistan.

Anyways, the war happened, and is still on; a framework of peace is being discussed between the warring parties where the elected legitimate government of Kabul has no seat. How can there be peace without engaging President Abdul Ghani's government in the talks and how credible Taliban's promises would be is a matter of separate discussion. As for now let us focus on the changing objectives and strategies of the war. The war on terror and the invasion of Afghanistan started with the main objective of rooting out

terrorism by capturing or killing Osama bin Laden, wiping out al-Qaeda and all its networks, eliminating Taliban or making it defunct and in the process democratizing Afghanistan. Although the global war on terror started with Afghanistan on the frontline, there was no definition of terrorism that included all (Rahman, 2010). Gradually and perhaps because of the failures that happened in the actual execution of the plan, the objectives of the war kept shifting and reshaped according to public opinion and to serve the interests of the forces that were fighting the war in the region. At times it focused on cutting down the Taliban and at others the focus was on rehabilitating and strengthening the political structures and other democratic institutions of the country, with recent focus apart from peace talks has been to train and support the native Afghan forces to combat the terrorists, who still maintain their stronghold in various parts of Afghanistan.

However, it would be wrong to say that the dominant US strategy did not work the way they hoped it would and to name one was the implementation of Counter-Insurgency (COIN). Nonetheless, the US-military policy makers and its administration have finally realized that COIN would not give the desired victory in Afghanistan or anywhere in the world. What they failed to understand is that more guns with people on a foreign territory will never win a war (hopefully they get that). The tragedy behind COIN was that it deluded the policy-makers into believing that if the military force was used in a certain manner it could give them political gains and outcomes further culminating into victory. Later on 2 May 2011, the main war objective of killing Osama bin Laden was achieved in Abbottabad; and soon after this the US intention of staying in Afghanistan were raised, with President Obama's administration calling back thousands of troops home in December 2014. The ones that remained were called the Resolute Action Force, with the primary objective of training and supporting the Afghan National Force to take over the combating operations and securing the region off Taliban. The inherent commitment on the part of US forces was to transition Afghanistan from an insecure environment towards stability and security giving the democratically elected government a chance to operate on its own. This transition to stability was to be ensured through the security platform and a continued process of capacity-building at all the levels of administration. However till date the Afghan National Army and the local forces have not achieved the level of self sustenance needed to combat the Taliban. On the other hand in the face of withdrawal of international forces Taliban has

upped its ante and taken over even more territories than what it had during the last decade. It now controls almost half of the country's territory and albeit two-thirds of its people.

According to UN reports released earlier this year, the civilian deaths have been more in 2018 than any other year since the Americans invaded Afghanistan⁷. Another report released by the UN Assistance Mission in Afghanistan (UNAMA), says that the International forces including NATO and the local Afghan army has killed more civilians than any other rebel or terrorist groups in the war-torn country⁸. In addition to this despite all the assistance it gets, due to nepotism and rampant corruption the government in Kabul is losing ground and the territories that it controlled. Taliban has intensified its military operations and attacks upon the security forces, though it has been in direct negotiations with the US since last year October, to find peace and end the war.

Is Peace Possible in the Current Situation?

After several tedious and failed attempts of restoring peace and stability in Afghanistan, the initiation of recent peace talks seem different as this time the two warring sides have decided to negotiate directly. Though it is welcoming but the absence of Kabul government from the table of peace talks raises a lot of questions behind the intentions of both the United States and Taliban. Currently there are two international efforts for peace underway – one is led by the US in Doha, Qatar, and the other is led by Russia in Moscow. The US led consultations is headed by Zalmay Khalilzad⁹, a Special Representative for Afghanistan Reconciliation, who after holding talks with various stakeholders like Saudi Arabia, Pakistan, Qatar and Taliban is expected to chalk a framework of peace so that US forces can honorably be withdrawn from a war which in words of President Trump is “ridiculous”. US want the Taliban to stop its bloody military campaign across the country and declare that it would not allow any other terrorist group to operate in the region; they want to chart out a plan of troops withdrawal with the exception of a small counter-terrorist force; and to push towards an intra-Afghan dialogue between Kabul government and Taliban to discuss the power sharing and future peace and political agendas.

Taliban on the other hand which has for a long time now, demanded withdraw of US troops, want Khalilzad to declare a timeline of US exit first, only after which there could be a deal. Taliban time and again has refused to talk to Kabul government as it considers it to be “illegitimate” and a US “puppet”. It seems Taliban is in no hurry to broker a peace framework. Moreover, refusing to

talk to or recognize Ghani's government is a strategy to delegitimize the powers that control Kabul. While engaging with the international stakeholders and whoever is ready to talk to them, Taliban is trying to gain legitimacy by projecting itself as the bigger player and perhaps the only actor capable of restoring peace in Afghanistan. The increased presence and lethality of Taliban in the recent years show that they want to strengthen their position and maximize their leverage when they speak at the negotiating table. Sher Mohammad Abbas Stanikzai, the one who represents Taliban in the talks is also under pressure from the military commander to wait until the Americans commit to withdraw before agreeing to anything.

The two-day conference held in Moscow in the month of February this year was the first occasion in years that the Afghans and Taliban met to discuss a peace framework to end the war. However, it was the officials from the opposition of the Afghan government that came to talk to the Taliban. President Ghani dismissed the Moscow talks saying that the ones who attended had no real negotiating authority. The government in Kabul is not wrong in questioning the motives of US-led peace talks with Taliban, which in a way was giving legitimacy to Taliban as a credible player in the country, which undermines their authority. The longer the Afghan government is kept out of the talks, the larger problem it encompasses. History is full of incidents where peace negotiations between the government and the insurgents is absolutely necessary to bring peace and detail out a framework for the same. Until an intra-Afghan dialogue happens its very difficult to say how successful the US-Taliban negotiations will be, whenever that might happen. The way Taliban refuses to talk to the Afghan government and insists that it would open a dialogue only after US withdraws its forces, is a condition that would be irrelevant as it seems that after the exit of forces the government might not exist in any meaningful way to negotiate a peace deal. It also shows that Taliban is negotiating from a strong position and even ruling out any power-sharing arrangement with the government; they also declined Loya Jirga's call for a ceasefire during Ramzaan.

In such a situation negotiating a peace deal and expecting that Taliban has had a change of heart and that it would comply with the peace agreements reflects the incompetent and myopic view of the American administrators and peace diplomats. US knows that the war is unwinnable, the last 18 years have proved that a military intervention is not the solution to the problem of insurgency and any prolonged occupation will not push Afghanistan towards peace let

alone a western-styled political system and democratic governance in a traditional and economically backward country. The only true prospect for peace can be through intra-Afghan dialogue, when all the stakeholders come together and discuss the future of their country that has been war-torn since four decades.

References

- NATO, (2001), “*Invocation of Article 5 Confirmed*”, October 3, <http://www.nato.int/update/2001/1001/e1002a.htm>
- Rappaport, U. (1982), “*John of Gischala: From Galilee to Jerusalem*”, JJS, 33, p 479-493.
- Washington Post, (2001), “*Bush Declares War*”, 20 September.
- Rahman, Khalid, (2010), “*Situation in Afghanistan and its Implications on the Central Asian Region*”, *International Seminar in Ashgabat, Security and Stability in Central Asia Interaction with International and Regional Organizations, UNRCCA*.

-
1. On 12th September 2001 President Bush addresses the nation declaring war and stating that US would use all its resources to defeat the enemy. On 20th September 2001, while addressing the joint session of the Congress and the nation he declares War on Terror in Afghanistan, *The Washington Post*, 20th September 2001.
 2. Article 5 of NATO states that, the signatories agree that an armed attack against is one or more of them in Europe or North America shall be considered an attack against them all (NATO, 2005)
 3. Apart from US and UK who began with the initial strikes , countries like France, Russia, China, India, Pakistan, Egypt, Iraq, the Central Asian Republics and the other NATO member states sent their troops to fight the US-led war against Terrorism.
 4. Sicarii: in Latin means dagger-man, this term was used for the Jewish zealots who fought the Roman occupation of Judea in an attempt to expel the Romans from the area. Although they were not terrorists in the modern sense but their method of killing in crowded places terrorized people.
 5. The US Department of State defines Terrorism as, premeditated and politically motivated violence against non-combatant targets by sub-national groups or clandestine agents, usually to influence an audience.
 6. Laub, Zachary, “*The Taliban in Afghanistan*”, 4th July, 2014, Council on Foreign Relations.
 7. UN Report 24 February 2019
 8. UNAMA, Quarterly Report on the Protection of Civilians in Armed Conflicts, 24 April 2019
 9. Zalmay Khalilzad is an American diplomat who served as US ambassador to the UN (2007-09), Iraq (2005-07 and Afghanistan (2003-05).
